

A REVIEW PAPER ON THE MEASUREMENT OF AUDIBLE NOISE GENERATED FROM HIGH-VOLTAGE TRANSMISSION LINES

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ABSTRACT

Transmission line construction is one among the foremost complex engineering projects. Measuring the parameters of a cable is far harder than measuring the other public infrastructure. The Geographic data system (GIS) is employed in several ways by cable designers but its use in measurement is restricted. This method will enhance the general public service provider involvement within the measurement process, and reduce the additional cost to live the side effects of the project. GIS is already utilized in cable Routing as a technical tool. This research applies GIS to extend the general public involvement within the Routing process and which further leads to reductions in time involved in approval of the road. This system reduces the general public resistance during the design and style process and allows more people to participate within the complex infrastructure planning and style problems.

Keywords: GIS, power system, FERC, EMF, AM, UHV.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indian Power transmission is that the one among largest electrical interconnected systems everywhere the planet. Transmission lines delivers and processes bulk electric power on its way from generating stations to distribution, which completes the processing and delivers it to consumers. Demand for electricity continuously also increases over time. so as to satisfy this demand, new generators are built. the facility from these generators will overload existing lines, so new lines are needed. Electricity was a regulated industry but Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC) requires wholesale electrical power trade open markets. As a result of this deregulation, electrical power is sold to the very best bidder. This open market is meant to permit utilities to sell and buy energy from other utilities regardless of distance. The transmission Grid is predicted to hold out such transactions within the utilities. These transactions are for financial reasons, not for the normal transmission function of reliability.

Load growth and open markets reduce the reliability and security of the facility system. Utility investment in new technologies like line upgrades, dynamic allocation and real time monitoring isn't enough to satisfy the specified reliability standards. These technologies aren't sufficient to enhance reliability during a deregulated environment. New Transmission Lines are required to satisfy the reliability needs of the system.

India is that the fifth biggest power generator within the world. As of March 31, 2008, it had a generation capacity of about 143 GW, with an annual output of over 700 billion units. The Indian economy is growing by 7-8 percent per annum. Its energy needs also are growing strongly, by 8-10 percent per annum. Over the last four years, by March 2012, the govt plans to extend the entire power generation capacity to 223 GW or 11.7 percent. the facility sector in India remains dominated by government-owned units, despite a move within the mid-1990s to open the world to non-public participation. The private sector accounts for less than 14 percent of the generation capacity and fewer than 10 percent of distribution. Its share of the transmission networks is even more insignificant, at but 1 percent.

II. TRANSMISSION LINE ROUTING MEASUREMENT

Transmission Line Routing Measurement may be a complex process which involves local, state and federal agencies. The permissible background level of the road is first approved by the state, usually a state commission, then it goes to federal agencies just like the Department of Energy (DOE) and FERC for approval. Depending upon the road background level, approval could also be required from several federal and state agencies. The cable measurement process is very complex, as transmission lines aren't aesthetically pleasing, and other people are concerned about health issues like EMF [7]. this might create a high level of public

opposition towards a line. Projects may face legal litigation from various stakeholders involved within the project if their concerns aren't properly addressed. Such legal litigation further delays the project. This end in a rise within the budget of the project and a stage may come at which the utility finds the project to be financially unfeasible. Ideally, this work should be wont to sufficiently well-designed that it might even be capable of improving the corridor planning process generally. this may introduce transparency and satisfaction for both the general public and planners.

III. TRANSMISSION LINES

A cable may be a specialized cable or other structure designed to conduct AC of frequency, that is, currents with a frequency high enough that their wave nature must be taken under consideration. A cable is employed for the transmission of electric power from generating substation to the varied distribution units. It transmits the wave of voltage and current from one end to a different. An Electrical Grid, or power system, is an interconnected network for delivering electricity from producers to consumers. Electrical Grids vary in size from covering one building through national grids (which cover whole countries) to transnational grids.

Fig-1: Block diagram of the Electrical Grid in India

IV. IMPACT OF NOISE

Much of the route of a cable goes through rural and undeveloped areas where there are more plants and animals than humans, so exposure of plants and animals to electric fields must be considered. Animals are shielded from electric fields by vegetation, and exposure is greatest once they are passing beneath transmission lines. Various studies are done on effects of electrical fields on animal behavior, melatonin production and immune function, and impacts found were low. Similar results were found in studies on plants. Construction activities like movement of heavy machinery, erection of towers and conductors end in noise round the line. The noise levels could also be objectionable if construction is just too on the brink of an urban area. Another source of noise from transmission lines is corona, for lines 345 kV and above [6]. this is often more prominent in foul weather and meteorological data shows that these conditions exist 7% of the time during a year. For a replacement line after construction, grease or oil on the surface of conductor are sources of corona. a replacement line has audible noise of fifty dBA round the ROW in foul weather [5, 6, 9].

Decibel: Since the unit decibel (dB) is usually utilized in RF engineering, a brief introduction and definition of terms is given here. The decibel is that the unit would not to express relative differences in signal power. it's expressed because the base-10 logarithm of the ratio of the powers of two signals:

$$P [dB] = 10 \cdot \log(P/P_0) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

It is also common to express the signal amplitude in dB. Since power is proportional to the square of a signal's amplitude, the voltage in dB is expressed as follows:

$$V [dB] = 20 \cdot \log(V/V_0) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Power transmission lines have substations at the beginning, end and in between. Audible noise [5] effects of sub-stations depend on the extent of ground noise existing round the substation. Switching and protection equipment installed in sub-station produces noise within the sort of low frequency hum. This noise depends upon the operating mode of the equipment installed.

Electromagnetic fields from transmission lines induce currents on objects within the proximity of the road. Certain circumstances, like contact of a grounded person with an ungrounded object under a high voltage line, may result during a nuisance shock or spark discharge. The magnitude of the induced current depends upon the electrical field intensity, size of the thing and insulation between object and ground. Magnetic fields also induce currents when objects like fences, pipelines and wires are in parallel with lines. The National Electrical Safety Code requires that for voltages quite 98 kV ac to ground the induced currents not be quite 5 mA. cable designers must design with enough clearances throughout the route of the road in order that line can meet these requirements. Inductive interference with pipelines must be considered during line design and route selection for a cable.

Engineering Features: cable routing not only depends upon non- technical factors like environmental and socio-economic, but also on engineering factors. Line designers need to carefully study and style the road to offer the simplest engineering solution for various problems like corona, interference, Noise, and natural factors like wind and ice.

Electromagnetic Interference: Electromagnetic interference is one among the main problems that designers face during the planning process. Corona [6] and gap discharges are the most sources of electromagnetic interference [2]. Corona is usually seen in 345 kV and better voltage transmission lines. electromagnetic wave from corona discharges affects AM radios, whereas gap discharges affect both television and radio reception. frequency emissions from corona occur between the ranges of 100 kHz to 2 MHz, and most communication systems like police, fire, commercial radios and cellular phones operate above 2 MHz. Broadcast AM radio, however, operates between 535 and 1604 kHz, and is thus often affected. Signal reflections from power transmission lines may cause ghosting in weak television signals. Electrical discharges between broken and loose hardware like insulators, clamps and brackets are transmitters of frequencies which will cause interference with some radio and tv signals. Interference depends upon the strength & quality of the transmitting signal, the space of the source to the receiver and therefore the quality of the radio or TV system.

V. RELATED WORK

Understanding the interference scenario in power lines network may be a key step to characterize the facility Line Communication (PLC) system. Emerging technologies related to conductors and transmission towers require a re-evaluation of models of audible noise generated by overhead line conductors [5]. Measurements on which existing commercial models were developed were typically performed on one, classical design of conductor around 50 years ago. For the characterization of components, systems and signals within the frequency (RF) and microwave ranges [3], several dedicated instruments are in use.

J. J. LaForest et al. [1, 1965] presented a way for calculating the static level of a cable where the static generation is produced by corona on station apparatus. Propagation of the static energy is described by a group of non-interacting transmission modes. a way has been presented for calculating the effect of single or multiple sources of station RI on the cable background level. J. R. Leslie et al. [2, 1971] intended to supply a comprehensive and coordinated summary of excellent engineering design practices for high-voltage transmission lines, which can end in a tolerable static level from the proposed line when placed in commission. Yokoshima Kato et al. [3, 1989] presented a way to form noise temperature correction [7] for the cable of a microwave thermal noise source by using three different transmission lines whose characteristics aren't necessarily just like each other.

K. Tanabe et al. [4, 1996] tested of asymmetrical bundles which have the potential to suppress corona activity. Spiral wires become the source of audible noise, that is, they contribute mainly to the rise of the extent of pure Tones which are of an equivalent frequency because the transmission lines and even higher harmonics of this

frequency. Hiroshi Nakanoal [5, 2002] verified the usefulness of an auxiliary cable method. Then this measurement result and a result calibrated to the noise source with two known standards are compared [5]. Corona is that the ionization of the air within the surrounding of the phase conductors and occurs within the case when electrical field on the surface of the conductors becomes larger than critical field for air, so that, at certain points, there's little or no discharge with pauses. Discharge causes specific noise and transmits radio-electric waves, the so-called "Radio-Electric Murmur" [6].

Friederike Hammersen et al. [7, 2016] state that Noise is often quantified by physical parameters, like dB measured at an edge round the house or within the home. The aims of the study were to look at the association between individual noise annoyance levels and psychological state of adults in Germany and to research whether this association varied with the source of environmental noise [13, 15]. With AM source noise has the foremost dramatic influence in additive phase noise. This work is an extension with a replacement comb design and measurements at the 10th harmonic employing a single channel phase noise system. This design is for a 100 MHz input with harmonics to a minimum of 1 GHz [8]. Gonghao Xie et al. [9, 2018] analyzed the audible noise of the cable. With the rapid development of UHV transmission technology, the continual improvement of voltage level has caused the deterioration of the electromagnetic environment, especially the audible noise. When the audible noise is detected indoors, the background noises are mainly generated by HVDC power source, which are easy to be estimated, thus this method are able to do an honest de-noising effect [6, 10].

VI. DIRECTIONS AND DISCUSSION

Nowadays, the continual increase within the voltage level of transmission lines makes corona problems became one among the most issues within the development of UHV transmission [2]. Compared with other electromagnetic environment problems like power frequency field, power frequency magnetic flux and radio interference, the effect of audible noise [5, 6] is that the most intuitive to the residents living within the vicinity of transmission lines, likely to cause psychological and physical discomfort, and is that the main source of public complaints about the grid. because the transmission corridors are getting increasingly tense, crossovers of overhead transmission lines with different voltage grades and structures are increasing. within the case of cross-over, the surface field intensity of the cable is harder to calculate than the standard single-circuit line, which makes the prediction of the noise distribution across the transmission lines more complicated [9].

Fig-2: Noise measurement at the Voltage levels w.r.to distance

Yingyi Liu et al. The article proposed by [10] was published in the year 2020, in which he majorized the audible noise at some transmission line stations in China. This measurement was done on phone numbers 25 26 and 28 where different voltages were flowing. 765 kilo volt current is flowing in our transmission line, so we have considered it appropriate to compare the measurements made in this work in 700 and 800 kilo volts with our proposed work. Measurement distances have been made at 0 meters 10 meters and 35 meters on all the poles.

The overall average audible noise was found to be 58.8 and 64.5 decibels, while in our proposed work, the 765-kilo volt transmission line at 6000, 600, 1500 and 400 meters is measured by 4G LTE networks at different distances. In future, this measurement will be done both day and night so that the average measurement of the whole day can be obtained.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Noise is an environmental burden whose health impacts are the topic of various studies. Noise annoyance in itself are often considered an environmental health risk [7, 6, 7]. Studies shows that lines have more outages in severe weather. Exposure to lightning strikes is far higher on a mountain top or ridge, which should be avoided as far as possible. The environment around a line, including wind, affects various electrical properties of the road. High velocity winds not only increase mechanical loading but also reduce the vertical and horizontal clearances. In regions where ice storms occur oscillations are produced near the elemental or at second or third harmonics, and this end in amplitudes as large as conductor sag. These two phenomena are found in both bundled also as single conductor lines. During planning stages line designers need to study the wind conditions of route that the road goes to follow before selection of the ultimate route. Line designers should avoid routes near agricultural fields like sugarcane, because a fireplace during a sugarcane field reduces air insulation.

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